

A NARRATIVE STUDY ON THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF A MOTHER DIAGNOSED WITH ADENOMYOSIS

A Research Study
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ABSTRACT

Adenomyosis, defined as the presence of endometrial glands and stroma infiltrating deep into the myometrium, is a common gynecologic disorder with poorly understood pathogenesis and pathophysiology. This study seeks to examine the lived experiences of a mother diagnosed with adenomyosis and assess the signs and symptoms experienced by the patient, focusing on physical and mental aspects. The study provides information about women suffering from this condition regarding the changes caused by the medical condition. Additionally, the study aims to understand the perceived experiences of the patient in terms of physical, emotional, and mental aspects. The study was conducted using narrative analysis involving a patient with adenomyosis. Data were collected through a checklist and a questionnaire and analyzed using thematic analysis. Our study reveals that the participant experiences heavy periods, pelvic pain, and feelings of sadness since being diagnosed. The participant also finds it hard to talk about it and feels lonely. The participant gets mad and upset about their condition. They cope by leaning on family, religion, and support groups. It's important for them to keep seeking help and finding ways to feel better.

Keywords: Adenomyosis, lived experiences, mother, signs and symptoms, physical health, mental health, pelvic pain, heavy periods, emotional impact, loneliness, coping mechanisms, family support, religion, support groups.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
TITLE PAGE	i
ABSTRACT	ii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	iii
LIST OF TABLES	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	v
LIST OF APPENDICES	vi
 Chapter	
1 THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING	
Introduction	1
Statement of the Problem	2
Scope and Delimitation	3
Significance of the Study	5
2 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES	
Discovery of Adenomyosis	6
Adenomyosis on Fertility	7
Signs of Adenomyosis	9
Symptoms of Adenomyosis	10
Coping Mechanism	13
Synthesis	15
Conceptual of Framework	18
Definition of Terms	19
3 METHODOLOGY	
Research Design	21
Sampling Techniques Procedure	22
Research Instrument	22
Data Gathering Procedures	24
Data Analysis	25
Risk and Safety	26
Ethical Considerations	27
4 PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA	
Physical signs and symptoms experienced	29
Mental signs and symptoms experienced	31

Physical, emotional, and mental checklist of the perceived experiences of the Mother with Adenomyosis	34
Social coping mechanisms used by the Mother with Adenomyosis	36
Mental coping mechanisms used by the Mother with Adenomyosis	38
Beliefs coping mechanisms used by the Mother with Adenomyosis	40
5 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
Summary of Findings	42
Salient Findings	43
Conclusions	44
Recommendations	45
BIBLIOGRAPHY	47
APPENDICES	54

LIST OF TABLES

Table		Page
1.1	Physical Signs and Symptoms Experienced	29
1.3	Mental Signs and Symptoms Experienced	32
2.1	Physical, Emotional, and Mental Checklist of the Perceived Experiences of the Mother with Adenomyosis	34
3.1	Social Coping Mechanisms Used by the Mother with Adenomyosis	36
3.2	Mental Coping Mechanisms Used by the Mother with Adenomyosis	38
3.3	Beliefs Coping Mechanisms Used by the Mother with Adenomyosis	40

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure		Page
1	Map of Solid Road, Barangay San Manuel, Puerto Princesa City, Palawan	4
2	Research Paradigm	18
3	Data Gathering Flowchart	24

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix		Page
A	Medical Certificate	54
B	Letter to the Gynecologist	56
C	Letter to the Principal	57
D	Parent Consent	58
E	Consent form from the Respondent	64
F	Interview Guide for the Gynecologist	65
G	Questionnaire for the Respondent	66
H	Checklist for the Respondent	67
I	Approval Form 1A	68
J	Approval Form 1B	71
K	Human Informed Consent Form	87
L	Photo Documents	89

CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

Introduction

Adenomyosis, defined as the presence of endometrial glands and stroma infiltrated deep and haphazardly into the myometrium, is a common gynecologic disorder with poorly understood pathogenesis and pathophysiology (Guo, 2020). Adenomyosis is commonly found in women of reproductive age. Most women with adenomyosis present with a wide range of symptoms, such as heavy menstruation, progressive dysmenorrhea, and a decline in fertility (Kunaseh et al., 2022). Adenomyosis often coexists with other gynecological comorbidities, such as endometriosis and uterine fibroids, and the diagnostic criteria are still not universally agreed. Therefore, the diagnostic process for adenomyosis is challenging (Chapron et al., 2020).

The association between adenomyosis and reproductive health seems to be prevalent which is concerning, posing a negative connection to a woman's potential to conceive (Buggio, L., et al, 2021). Adenomyosis appears to be associated with a 28% reduction in the chances for clinical pregnancy and with more than a doubled risk for miscarriage (Vercellini, P., et al, 2019). In addition, association with reproductive issues seems to be similar after age adjustments (Nirgianakis, K., et al, 2021). The medical condition seems to have a detrimental impact on pregnancy outcomes, a higher chance of premature birth, pre-eclampsia, and complications with pregnancy (Razavi, M., et al, 2019).

As awareness about gynecological health continues to grow, there are increasing conditions such as adenomyosis, which has been observed as a trending health issue in countries like the Philippines. This is relevant as it sheds

light on the experiences of mothers diagnosed with adenomyosis, adenomyosis is a common but often under-recognized gynecological disorder. Some studies state that no matter what treatment is given, patients are always at risk of recurrence, especially for young, conservative patients (Huang, R, et al, 2023). By understanding the stories and challenges faced by mothers with this condition, healthcare providers and policymakers can gain valuable insights to better support women with adenomyosis.

Statement of the Problem

1. What are the signs and symptoms experienced by the mother before being diagnosed with Adenomyosis in terms of:
 - a. Physical
 - b. Mental

2. What are the perceived experiences of a mother diagnosed with Adenomyosis in terms of:
 - a. Physical
 - b. Emotional
 - c. Mental

3. What are common coping mechanisms used by a mother diagnosed with Adenomyosis when dealing with their medical condition in terms of:
 - a. Social Coping
 - b. Emotional Coping
 - c. Spiritual Coping

Assumptions

Participants' experiences before and after adenomyosis diagnosis lack consistent themes and show little variation in perceived experiences and coping mechanisms.

Participants' experiences before and after adenomyosis diagnosis demonstrate consistent themes, varied perceived experiences, and multiple coping mechanisms.

Scope and Delimitation

This study is delimited on the following:

Problem. This study titled “**A Narrative Study on the Lived Experiences of A Mother Diagnosed with Adenomyosis**” would examine the lived experiences of a mother diagnosed with adenomyosis. The purpose of the research is to assess the signs and symptoms experienced by the patient focusing on the physical and mental experiences. However, the study would not assess the other experiences of the mother. In addition, this study aimed to understand the perceived experiences encountered by the patient in terms of Physical, Emotional, and Mental. Moreover, this aimed to identify what are the common coping mechanisms used by the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis, highlighting the social coping, emotional coping, and spiritual coping mechanisms.

At the end of this study, it is expected to create a video documentary which would feature interviews with a mother who has been diagnosed with adenomyosis, along with OB-GYN (obstetrician-gynecologist) discussing the condition. The researchers used semi-structured interviews, checklists, close-ended questions, and articles related to the lived experiences of a mother

diagnosed with adenomyosis in seeking answers to the statement of the problem of this study. The study delimits the interview to only 1 mother who is clinically diagnosed with adenomyosis. The method of data collection was face-to face and the researcher used semi-structured questionnaires.

Locale. The study would be conducted at Brgy. Jolo, where the respondent is diagnosed with adenomyosis, and an interview would be conducted at the location.

The map of Purok Masipag located in Brgy. Jolo, Municipality of Roxas, Palawan, Philippines is presented.

Figure 1. Map of Brgy Jolo, Municipality of Roxas, Palawan

Time Frame. The study started on February 27, 2024, and ended on May 5, 2024.

Significance of the Study

This study aimed to determine the experiences of a mother suffering from adenomyosis. The general intent of this study is to provide information about women suffering from this condition regarding the changes that the medical condition caused.

For the Patients with Adenomyosis, This study would provide patients with adenomyosis with increased awareness and understanding of the condition, enabling better-informed decisions about their health, treatment options, and potential risks associated with adenomyosis.

For the City Health Centers, After finalizing the findings of this study, city health centers can improve medical consultations, counseling services, and health education for adenomyosis patients at the local level, potentially leading to more effective outcomes for patients.

For the Department of Health (DOH), This study's findings would allow the DOH to enhance their guidelines on health related to management of adenomyosis patients, which would result in improving the quality of care for affected individuals across the country.

For Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth), PhilHealth can expect insights to expand their coverage and reimbursement policies for treatments related to adenomyosis, ensuring equitable access to healthcare services.

For the Future Researchers, After this research, future researchers can expect this study to serve as a valuable reference, providing a foundation for further investigations aimed to improve coping mechanisms, and outcomes of patients with adenomyosis.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents the relevant literature and studies local or foreign taken from some books, journals, published thesis and dissertations, and from the internet.

A. Discovery of Adenomyosis

Adenomyosis is a condition in which endometrial tissue grows within the uterus' muscle walls. Its diagnosis, management, and understanding have evolved over time. Adenomyosis was first observed by a German pathologist named Carl von Rokitansky described a histopathologic finding, which he called "cystosarcoma adenoids uterinum" in 1860 and Thomas Cullen in 1896 laid the groundwork for the understanding of adenomyosis. However, it was not until 1925 when J. Sampson coined the term "adenomyosis" that a specific name for this condition emerged. And in 1972, Bird provided the contemporary definition of adenomyosis, which states that it is the benign invasion of endometrium into the myometrium (Benagiano et al., 2014).

In the past, the diagnosis of the condition required a biopsy or hysterectomy, which was an invasive procedure. However, with the advancement of medical technology, non-invasive methods such as ultrasound or MRI scans can now diagnose it. In the case of women who no longer desire pregnancy, a definitive treatment option is hysterectomy. However, for women who wish to preserve fertility or avoid extensive surgery, a range of medical and less invasive therapies are available (Benagiano et al., 2014).

While adenomyosis shares similar clinical features with endometriosis, it differs in its gross, histological, and clinical manifestations and risk factors

(Habiba et al., 2023). Adenomyosis involves the invasion of endometrial tissue into the myometrium (Porter & Goldstein, 2019), whereas endometriosis is characterized by the presence of ectopic endometrial tissue outside the uterus (Parasar et al., 2017). Additionally, Polycystic ovarian syndrome is also a well-known endocrine condition among women of this generation. Symptoms of hyperandrogenism, irregular menstrual periods, and insulin resistance are all traits associated with PCOS. In women with PCOS, the chance of having problems including infertility, insulin resistance, and type 2 diabetes increases (Zehravi, M., 2022).

Despite advancements in diagnostic techniques, Identifying adenomyosis with precision can be difficult because its symptoms overlap with those of other gynecological conditions such as chronic pelvic pain, menorrhagia, metrorrhagia, dysmenorrhea, and dyspareunia (Chen et al., 2019). Additionally, the prevalence of adenomyosis in various populations is not well-established, and the understanding of the early stages of the ailment remains limited (Habiba & Benagiano, 2021).

By recognizing specific pathways and factors, future interventions may offer more personalized and effective management strategies for people with this condition.

B. Adenomyosis on Fertility

An essential component of a woman's reproductive health is her fertility. It is essential in molding the lives of individuals, families, and society institutions. As Davis (2021) stated, fertility is a person's ability to bear children. It requires the production of enough healthy sperm by the male and usable eggs by the female (Britannica, 2024). Adenomyosis can affect the fertility of a woman.

Women with adenomyosis were detected by ultrasound and had significantly reduced clinical pregnancy rates (23.6%). Also, several studies have shown that the existence of adenomyosis can disabled a woman to reproduce by affecting the utero tubal transport and altering endometrial function and receptivity of a woman's body (Harada et al., 2016). In addition, growing maternal age is linked to adenomyosis, which is linked to decreased pregnancy rates because of decreased ovarian reserve and oocyte quality (Günther et al., 2022).

In cases of adenomyosis, It highlights the cautions, seriousness, influence, and danger of adenomyosis on a woman's fertility. It is important to keep in mind that having this medical condition is scary for every woman because the availability of carrying a child can be taken away. It really affects the individuality, character, emotional, and reproductive outcomes of a woman.

This research is aimed at assessing the role that adenomyosis plays in women's fertility. The researchers goal is to present a thorough understanding of the effects of adenomyosis on the fertility of a woman by looking at variables such as condition severity, and reproductive history. This information can help with early detection and management of reproductive problems associated with adenomyosis and can also guide clinical practice.

In conclusion, adenomyosis represents a significant risk factor that affects their fertility in women. By recognizing the impact of this condition on fertility outcomes, healthcare professionals can provide targeted counseling and support to affected individuals. This research aimed to expand this understanding by researching all the variables that affect the fertility of a woman related to adenomyosis. By raising awareness and doing thorough assessments, the researchers may work to enhance the treatment and results of infertility related to adenomyosis.

C. Signs Of Adenomyosis

On histology, adenomyosis is characterized by the presence of ectopic endometrial mucosa within the myometrium (invagination of endometrium in the myometrium at a depth of at least 2.5 mm below the basal layer of the endometrium) that leads to hypertrophy of the smooth muscle, which confirms the diagnosis. It can be either focal (one or several foci in the myometrium; these are nodular in the case of adenomyoma) or diffuse (numerous foci spread throughout the myometrium) and it is often asymmetric, predominating in the posterior uterine corpus (Levy, G., et al., 2014). It is associated with heavy menstrual bleeding, pain, and infertility. Known risk factors for adenomyosis include multiparity, early menarche, obesity, and previous uterine surgeries or interventions (Decter, et al., 2021). Furthermore, adenomyosis often coexists with other gynecological comorbidities, such as endometriosis and uterine fibroids, and the diagnostic criteria are still not universally agreed. Therefore, the diagnostic process for adenomyosis is challenging (Chapron, Charles, et al., 2020).

Until recently, adenomyosis was a clinically neglected condition. Nowadays, adenomyosis may also be diagnosed by non-invasive techniques, because of imaging advancements. Thus, a new epidemiological scenario has developed with an increasing number of women of reproductive age with ultrasound (US) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) diagnosis of adenomyosis. This condition is associated with a wide variety of symptoms (pelvic pain, AUB), but it is also recognised that some women are asymptomatic.

Adenomyosis is still difficult to diagnose, even with advances in diagnostic imaging, and it frequently co-occurs with other disorders such as endometriosis and uterine fibroids. Furthermore, the co-occurrence of this medical condition

with other gynecological disorders such as endometriosis and uterine fibroids often exacerbates its clinical presentation, which can range from pelvic pain to infertility. Therefore, despite the fact that technology has made adenomyosis more well known, the process of diagnosis is still difficult and highlights the complexity of this mysterious condition.

To summarize, adenomyosis is a complicated uterine condition distinguished by the invasion of endometrial tissue into the myometrium. Despite recent advances in diagnostic imaging techniques, adenomyosis remains difficult to identify, frequently coexisting with other gynecological disorders such as endometriosis and uterine fibroids. The study's goal is to investigate the lived experiences of mothers who have been diagnosed with adenomyosis, offering light on the physical, emotional, mental, and consequences of the medical condition. This study emphasizes the need of non-invasive diagnostic approaches and the complexity of adenomyosis, highlighting the need for additional research and increased awareness among both patients and medical professionals. Finally, the goal is to contribute to a better knowledge of adenomyosis in order to improve future patient care and results.

D. Symptoms of Adenomyosis

Adenomyosis is a common gynecologic condition characterized by invasion of endometrial glands and stroma within the myometrium. Resulting in abnormal uterine bleeding, pelvic pain, and infertility (Bourdon, M., et al, 2021). Symptoms that are historically attributed to endometriosis may actually be caused by adenomyosis. Adenomyosis remains a challenge to identify, assess and research because of the lack of standardized diagnostic criteria, especially in women who wish to retain their uterus (Isaacson, K. 2020). According to other

studies, symptoms of adenomyosis typically arise between 40 and 50 years of age (Cunningham RK. et al, 2018). Patients with adenomyosis may eventually have a hysterectomy if symptoms are not controlled with medical therapy (Schrager, S. et al, 2022). Adenomyosis continues to mystify scientists, gynecologists, and patients alike. A lack of standard histopathologic and imaging diagnoses makes this medical condition challenging to study (Loring, M, et al, 2021).

Adenomyosis is a heterogeneous gynaecologic condition with a range of clinical presentations, the most common being heavy menstrual bleeding and dysmenorrhoea; however, patients can also be asymptomatic (Pontis, A., et. al., 2016). Adenomyosis remains a challenge to identify, assess and research because of the lack of standardized diagnostic criteria, especially in women who wish to retain their uterus (Isaacson, K., & Loring, M., 2020). Adenomyosis occurs in 8.8% to 61.5% of women undergone hysterectomy, and rates vary widely by differences in diagnostic criteria and variations between and within pathologists. 1, 2 The prevalence is estimated to range from 20% to 34%, based on patients referred for pelvic imaging rather than the general population of women (Kho, K. A., et. al. 2021).

The authors address symptoms of adenomyosis. They agree on different clinical presentations, including heavy periods, painful periods and sometimes having no symptoms but also emphasize that diagnosing it may be quite challenging given the lack of standardized criteria. It is also noted that prevalence rates differ greatly depending on diagnostic criteria and pathologists' differences. According to the authors, advanced imaging techniques such as transvaginal sonography and magnetic resonance imaging play a major role in enhancing comprehension and diagnosis.

According to the authors, heavy periods and painful menstruation are often claimed, some women do not realize they have it. Still, making a diagnosis for adenomyosis becomes difficult because there are no standardized criteria especially in situations where women want to keep their uterus intact. The frequency of adenomyosis is quite variable with different diagnostic criteria and pathologists' interpretations resulting in estimates ranging from 8.8% to 61.5% among those undergoing hysterectomy and 20% to 34% when referred for pelvic imaging.

The authors also stated that heavy period bleeding and painful periods are common symptoms, but more symptoms like pelvic pain, pressure, and changes in period cycles should be included. This would give a better understanding of the condition. It would help to explain the challenges in diagnosing adenomyosis. This includes symptoms that are similar to other women's health problems. Also, the limits of the tests used and the need for clear diagnosis criteria are important. Adding more detail about the wide range of how common adenomyosis is would make the explanation better. This includes reasons for the differences in how often it happens, like differences in who is studied and where they are. Talking about new ways to diagnose adenomyosis and research to make diagnosis and treatment better would also improve the explanation. It shows that the area is changing and efforts are being made to help women with adenomyosis.

E. Coping Mechanism

Adenomyosis, a complex uterine disorder, significantly impacts the lives of mothers diagnosed with the condition. One of the coping mechanisms used by caregivers of mental disease patients is spirituality. Health is not only physical, psychological, mental and social, but also a spiritual wellbeing. Spirituality is the power beyond the individual and his being. So it is personal awareness that covers both the physical field and beyond (F Gök, et. al., 2017). According to a study, people who have been diagnosed with a medical condition are likely to cope by participating in spiritual activities like prayer, religious attendance, or other types of spiritual expression. These activities may enhance the patients' overall wellbeing and psychological strength while they undergo medical treatment (Ahmadi, 2018).

According to Ahmadi, 2018, faith and spiritual practices significantly impact participants' medical condition perceptions and coping procedures regardless of resettlement country or gender. Several themes emerged: participants believe in the interdependent relationship between mental and cognitive health. There is a self-awareness of the impact of the refugee experience and trauma on participants' mental health problems, leading to a belief of increased personal risk for developing dementia. Spiritual fatalism (belief that events are predetermined by God, fate, or destiny) greatly informs these perceptions of mental and cognitive health. Participants acknowledge that practicing faith improves their mental and cognitive health, and many read scripture to prevent dementia. And finally, spiritual gratitude and trust are important coping procedures that build resilience among participants (Bridi, L., et. al, 2023).

The study by Huang, R. et al (2023) provided insights into the barriers to self-management of patients with adenomyosis, including physical, psychological, daily life, and self-image problems. The patients also needed emotional and social support, which recommended that professionals should provide authoritative health education and multiple forms of support. Additionally, while adenomyosis can disrupt your social life, remember to carve out time for self-care. Whether it's a quiet evening at home or a leisurely walk, prioritizing your well-being can help you retain your sense of self (Sundaram, B. 2023, June). Furthermore, according to Cope, A. G. et al (2020, May) there is no approved medical therapy for adenomyosis and limited evidence to guide treatments in part due to the complexity of non-histologic diagnosis and the prevalence of concomitant gynecologic conditions.

The concept provides a comprehensive overview of the challenges associated with adenomyosis and highlights the importance of exploring coping mechanisms. It acknowledges the complexity of treatment options and the need for further research due to the limited evidence available.

Given the complexity and impact of adenomyosis on women's lives, it is imperative to delve deeper into understanding the coping mechanisms used by mothers facing this condition. Research in related fields, adenomyosis is associated with infertility, and coping mechanisms like oral contraceptive pills, anti-prostaglandins, and progestins can help manage menstrual pain and menorrhagia. M. Szubert et al.(2021). These insights highlight the importance of exploring coping mechanisms as a means of navigating the complexities of adenomyosis and improving the quality of life for affected individuals. By elucidating the coping mechanisms used by these individuals, the researchers

seek to inform the development of comprehensive support interventions tailored to their unique needs and circumstances.

In summary, the exploration of coping mechanisms among mothers facing adenomyosis is essential for enhancing the researchers' understanding of this complex condition and improving patient outcomes. By acknowledging the challenges and gaps in existing research, and by conducting thorough investigations into coping strategies, the researchers can pave the way for more effective management and support for individuals living with adenomyosis.

Synthesis

Adenomyosis is a complex disorder within the muscular wall of the uterus. The disruption between the deepest layer of the endometrium leading to tissue complications (Taren, et al., 2014). Similarly, a similar tissue grows outside the uterus (WHO, 2023). Adenomyosis and Endometriosis are similar to how the uterine lining develops, differing by location within the muscular layer and outside the uterus respectively. The sickness has a global impact, yet there are substantial delays with diagnosis (Johnson, et al., 2016). This medical condition can cause problems in a woman's health such as pelvic pain, irregular bleeding, and difficulties with fertility (Greene, et al., 2015).

When endometrial glands and stroma are pathologically visible within the uterine myometrium, the condition known as adenomyosis occurs in a benign manner (S. Vannuccini, et al., 2019). The pathogenesis involves sex steroid hormone abnormalities, inflammation, fibrosis, and neuroangiogenesis, even though the proposed mechanisms are not fully understood. For many years, adenomyosis has been considered a histopathological diagnosis made after hysterectomy, classically performed in perimenopausal women with abnormal

uterine bleeding (AUB) or pelvic pain (G. Weiss et al., 2015). Until recently, adenomyosis was a clinically neglected condition. Nowadays, adenomyosis may also be diagnosed using non-invasive techniques because of imaging advancements. Similarly, adenomyosis often coexists with other gynecological comorbidities, such as endometriosis and uterine fibroids, and the diagnostic criteria are still not universally agreed upon (V. Aleksandrovykh et al., 2018). Therefore, the diagnostic process for adenomyosis is challenging. (Chapron, Charles, et al., 2020)

Adenomyosis, a challenging uterine disorder occurs in women in their reproductive years, which may result with physical, mental, and emotional issues (Garcia, et al., 2011). According to Han, L. et al (2023), continuous exploration of the treatment of adenomyosis patients with new drugs, surgical methods, and treatment concepts appear. It's essential to provide new insights into the barriers of self-management of patients with adenomyosis, especially with mental health, as stated by Shree IVF Clinic (2023). A balanced diet rich in anti-inflammatory foods, regular exercise, and stress management techniques such as yoga and mindfulness can help reduce symptoms and improve overall well being. There is still no approved medical therapy for adenomyosis and limited evidence to guide treatments in part due to the complexity and the prevalence of concomitant gynecologic conditions, highlighting a need to address the coping mechanisms of mothers diagnosed with adenomyosis when dealing with their medical condition (Cope, A., et al., 2020).

Adenomyosis is understood as a complex disorder occurring within the muscular wall of the uterus, characterized by the disruption of the deepest layer of the endometrium, leading to tissue complications. The diagnosis is connected to the low pregnancy rate, which shows that it has the capability to disable a

woman's ability to reproduce. The leading cause of adenomyosis is structural distortion in the uterine myometrium, causing sex hormone abnormalities, inflammation, fibrosis, and neuroangiogenesis. Treatment options include new drugs, surgical methods, and lifestyle interventions like a balanced diet, exercise, and stress management techniques. However, there is no approved medical therapy for adenomyosis, and treatment guidance is limited due to its complexity.

Ahmadi, 2018, stated that faith and spiritual practices or beliefs significantly impact participants' medical condition perceptions and coping procedures regardless of resettlement country or gender. Therefore faith and spiritual practices or beliefs would affect the person diagnosed with adenomyosis. According to Medical News Today, 2022, adenomyosis is a medical condition. If applied, belief directly impacts adenomyosis patient's coping mechanism.

Conceptual Framework

A study would be conducted through narrative analysis. The conceptual framework of the study is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2. Research Paradigm

Figure 2 shows the research paradigm of the study, containing the input as the signs and symptoms experienced by the mother before being diagnosed with Adenomyosis in terms of; physical, and mental. Perceived experiences of the mother diagnosed with Adenomyosis in terms of; physical, emotional, and mental. Common coping mechanisms used by the mother diagnosed with Adenomyosis when dealing with their illness in terms of; social coping, emotional coping, and beliefs coping.

The process shows the respondent interview, using a semi-structured interview, providing the checklist for the perceived experiences, narrative, and thematic analysis. For the output, the researchers are expected to provide the

determined signs and symptoms based on the thematic analysis, the determined the perceived experiences based on the checklist, and the determined the common coping mechanisms used by the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis based on the thematic analysis. Lastly, the researchers would also provide a documentary video.

Definition of Terms

In order to facilitate a common understanding of the information conveyed in this research study, these terms are hereby defined operationally and theoretically. For clarification, the important term used in the study has been defined.

Adenomyosis - A condition in which endometrial tissue grows within the uterus' muscle walls.

Coping Mechanisms - Strategies used by mother to manage adenomyosis challenges, including social, emotional, and belief.

Convenience - Refers to ease or suitability, often related to making something more accessible or manageable without excessive difficulty or inconvenience.

Endometriosis - Refers to the presence of ectopic endometrial tissue outside the uterus

Fertility - A woman's ability to bear children.

Gynecologic disorder - A condition that affects the normal function of female reproductive organs.

Myometrium - The muscular wall of the uterus that undergoes significant changes in size and cellular properties in specific physiological and pathological conditions.

Narrative - The way a story or account is structured, conveying events and experiences in a coherent sequence, often with a beginning, middle, and end.

Purposive - Intentional or deliberate, suggesting that actions or choices are made with a specific goal or purpose in mind.

Spiritual Coping - Coping mechanisms regarding religious activities and faith.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter provides the details that aim to point out the methodological procedures by which the data relevant to the problem statement of the study were collected. It outlined the research design, which emphasized how the study was structured, the sampling technique used in choosing the respondents, the instrumentation employed to gather data, the organized data gathering procedures, and the data analysis. It also further highlights the importance of considering any potential risk and safety, as well as the ethical considerations and practices associated with the study.

Research Design

The researchers conducted qualitative research in the form of Narrative Research. According to Vanderpool (2014), narrative research entails gathering personal accounts or stories from individuals about a specific phenomenon. The aim of this study is to identify the perceived experiences of a mother who is affected by adenomyosis in terms of emotional, mental, and physical. The narrative design is an appropriate type of research design for this study because it explores the story of a mother who is affected by adenomyosis or to learn about their experiences. Moreover, narrative research consists only of 1-2 respondents, and this study aimed to gather data from one adenomyosis patient. The narratives in this research would be analyzed qualitatively to identify common themes and patterns in the patients' both perceived experiences and experiences only through an interview, questionnaire, and checklist. The study's research questions can also be answered by using this design to collect data and learn about the participants' experiences.

Sampling Techniques Procedure

In this narrative research, the researchers used a purposive sampling to specifically target participant(s) diagnosed with adenomyosis. This sampling technique ensures selection of an individual whose experiences could offer deep insights into the intersection of motherhood, infertility, and adenomyosis. Purposive sampling, as explained by Kassiani Nikolopoulou (2022), involves selecting units based on specific characteristics required for the sample, thereby ensuring a deliberate and targeted approach to participant selection.

Additionally, convenience sampling was incorporated in this research as the respondent is someone connected to the researchers. According to Nikolopoulou (2022), convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling method where units are selected for its ease of access to the researcher. In this case, the researcher has a colleague with a mother that was diagnosed with adenomyosis. This narrative study aimed to provide insights into the lived experiences of the individual sampled in the context of this medical condition.

Research Instrument

This narrative study used semi structured interviews and checklists to explore the experiences of mothers diagnosed with adenomyosis. The interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner, covering topics such as medical journeys, emotional and physical well-being, influence on social interactions, coping techniques, and familial dynamics. The checklist served as a structured tool to ensure that all relevant topics were covered during the interview with mothers diagnosed with adenomyosis.

The study aimed to investigate the emotional, mental, and social effects of adenomyosis on mothers, as well as to determine commonly used coping

mechanisms among affected women, including social, emotional, and potentially religious aspects of their lives. To ensure ethical standards and compliance, the participants were provided with an informed consent form, interview guide, and permission letter. Additionally, the participants' were informed about the use of smartphones as audio recorders, pens and paper for taking notes of the important information the participants' stated, and a Nikon camera for recording the entire interview process.

This study held significant importance in providing valuable insights into the distinct challenges experienced by mothers affected by adenomyosis, ultimately aiming to improve support and care for this specific demographic.

Data Gathering Procedures

Figure 3: Data Gathering Flowchart

Figure 3 shows the process of gathering the data. Initially, the researchers sought permission from the school principal, administrators, head, and the teacher of Palawan National School. After seeking permission, the researchers would then proceed in creating the interview guide which contains different questions derived from the research questions and research objectives.

The selection of the participant would also be done by using convenience and purposive sampling. Convenience sampling is commonly used in situations where researchers have limited time, resources, or access to the population they wish to study. In addition, purposive sampling involves selecting participants based on specific criteria such as expertise, experience, or unique perspectives.

The participants were selected based on their medical diagnosis, ensuring their firsthand experience to the study's focus. Additionally, the researchers oriented the participant regarding the purpose and procedures that came through this research study, along with the importance of their involvement

for this research. Respecting the participants' autonomy, the researchers asked for informed consent before allowing them to make autonomous decisions about their involvement. Finally, video and audio recording together with the checklist and interview guide were set up as the conduction of the interview began.

Data Analysis

In the data analysis, the data collected by the researchers are evaluated and interpreted here. Narrative analysis distinguishes itself from other qualitative methods by its focus on narrated experiences representing either the full life story or aspects of it (Cissè, & Rasmussen. 2022). The researchers employed narrative analysis to explore the experiences of the mother before being diagnosed with adenomyosis. The researchers would also provide a checklist regarding the perceived experiences for the post-diagnosis of adenomyosis, from Barangay Jolo, Roxas City, Palawan. Using this method, the researchers can assess the information from a number of sources, including and interviews with the participants. The analysis of how people think and communicate about their experiences comes up with rich and detailed information about how individuals perceive their lives.

In addition, this study used a thematic method to analyze the data obtained in order to describe and determine the findings of the responses. Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data, it is usually applied to a set of texts, such as an interview or transcripts. The researchers closely examine the data to identify common themes – topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly (Caulfield, 2019), and according to Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis method is a repetitive process consisting of six steps. The first step is becoming familiar with the data, second is generating codes,

third is generating themes, fourth is reviewing themes, fifth is defining and naming themes, and lastly is finding examples.

Lastly, a checklist, and a questionnaire were used to analyze the perceived experiences of the mother who is diagnosed with adenomyosis in terms of physical, emotional, and mental. Based on Pritha Bhandari, 2021, checklists are commonly used in market research as well as in the social and health sciences. And based on Nelson E. 2017, a checklist is a form that is used for quickly and easily recording data or identifying actions or requirements.

Risk and Safety

Conducting a narrative study on a mother diagnosed with adenomyosis involves several considerations for risk and safety during data gathering. The data gathering process may require close interaction with the respondent, potentially causing pressure or emotional distress. Regarding data collection, the study would be conducted outside the campus, and specifically would be conducted in the respondent's house, researchers may encounter unfamiliar locations that may get them lost.

The researchers should also be cautious about interacting with dogs, considering the risk of bites. To address the risk, the researchers would ensure physical guidance by the respondent's daughter. By addressing these considerations, the study can be conducted responsibly while prioritizing the well-being of the researchers and respondent.

Ethical Considerations

The present study ensured the well-being, safety, and rights of the patient involved. Firstly, obtaining informed consent from the patient is essential, emphasizing the need for understandable information about the study, including its purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Moreover, ensuring the confidentiality and privacy of the participant's personal and medical information is crucial, safeguarding their sensitive data from unauthorized access or disclosure. Additionally, this study would be conducted in a manner that would avoid any potential physical or psychological harm to the patient.

The provided interview guide helped the researchers to avoid the use of inappropriate words that would lessen any adverse effects that may arise during the research process. Lastly, this research adhered to the principles of transparency and responsible conduct, maintaining the highest standards of ethical and professional practice throughout all phases of the study.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter mainly presents the analysis and interpretation of data used in the study. The data is presented and arranged according to the questions raised in the statement of the problem in chapter 1.

The following are the data sets that the researchers have gathered during the interview. The data was gathered by talking to the respondent using an interview guide. Researchers were able to talk to the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis who were willing to participate in the study.

Statement of the Problem 1. What are the signs and symptoms experienced by the mother before being diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

a. Physical

b. Mental

Problem 1

a. Have you experienced severe abdominal pain, prolonged menstruation, severe pelvic pain during the menstruation period?

b. Does the physical pain disrupt your daily activities? (yes or no)

If yes, how? If not, why?

Table 1.1 Physical Signs and Symptoms Experienced

Respondents	Key Quote(s)	Code(s)	Theme(s)
M 1	<p>Yes, sometimes before menstruation, my lower abdomen hurts immediately, about once, uh... One week before my period arrives, my lower abdomen starts to hurt. When my period comes, the pain gets severe.</p> <p>No, just three days, three to four days only. I bled continuously. I bled, and the folk chiropractor said I was pregnant, but the bleeding continued for 2 weeks. I decided to go to a doctor, and then I found out that I wasn't pregnant.</p> <p>Yes, my pelvic area did hurt when I went to the Doctor. It's really just my lower abdomen itself, even my waist or pelvic area that's hurting.</p> <p>Yes, when I'm working, because if my lower abdomen hurts, I can't work well. I can't finish my work. I just rested. I can't work anymore.</p>	<p>Lower abdomen pain</p> <p>Severe pain</p> <p>No prolonged menstruation</p> <p>Past prolonged menstruation</p> <p>Pain is the pelvic area</p> <p>Affected daily activities</p>	<p>The physical signs and symptoms experienced by the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis.</p>

Table 1.1 shows the signs and symptoms experienced by respondent M 1 before being diagnosed with adenomyosis in terms of physical and mental. Based on the collected information, the respondent experienced significant challenges related to their menstrual cycle. Notably, M 1 mentioned that she experienced lower abdominal pain a week before her period and it gets severe when her menstrual cycle starts. She also experienced excessive menstrual bleeding thus impacting her ability to concentrate and affected her daily activities. The data demonstrated that these signs and symptoms had an impact on the mother's well-being even before she consulted a doctor.

The respondent stated:

"Oo, minsan bago magkaroon ng regla, biglaang sumasakit ang puson ko, mga isang beses, uh... Isang linggo bago dumating ang regla ko, nagsisimula nang masakit ang puson ko. Kapag dumating na ang regla ko, lumalala ang sakit."

Yes, sometimes before menstruation, my lower abdomen hurts immediately, about once, uh... One week before my period arrives, my lower abdomen starts to hurt. When my period comes, the pain gets severe.

"Dinugo ako ng tuloy-tuloy. Dinugo ako, at sabi ng manghihilot na buntis ako, pero nagpatuloy ang pagdurugo ng dalawang linggo. Nagpasiya akong magpunta sa doktor, at doon ko natuklasan na hindi ako buntis."

I bled continuously. I bled, and the folk chiropractor said I was pregnant, but the bleeding continued for 2 weeks. I decided to go to a doctor, and then I found out that I wasn't pregnant.

According to Schrage, et. al. (2022), adenomyosis is a clinical condition where endometrial glands are found in the myometrium of the uterus. One in three patients with adenomyosis is asymptomatic, but the rest may present signs and symptoms such as heavy menstrual bleeding, pelvic pain, or infertility. Heavy menstrual bleeding is the most common symptom.

a. What was your reaction when you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

b. Have you ever felt fear and experienced depression when you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

Table 1.2. Mental Signs and Symptoms Experienced

Respondents	Key Quote(s)	Code(s)	Theme(s)
M 1	<p>It seems like I'm happy with the result because the doctor initially told me that my uterus should be removed right away because it's dangerous, but when I consulted another doctor, he said that the cysts were okay, they weren't growing, but he said I have adenomyosis.</p> <p>No, it's okay. At first, I really cried when my first doctor told me because I searched Dermoid Cysts on Google and it said there that if neglected, it can turn into a tumor. That's why I really cried when I came back from the doctor.</p> <p>Yes I felt depressed, I said "ouch", I said... What do you call this? Her solution, it's still removal, I said. The uterus, it's expensive. I asked the Doctor, they have the same price as the other Doctor, around 100k... It's expensive. So I said I'll just wait, that's why I always pray about it.</p>	<p>Happy with the latest result</p> <p>Emotional relief</p> <p>Cried</p> <p>Depressed</p> <p>Too expensive of a surgery</p> <p>Faithfulness</p>	<p>Mental signs and symptoms of the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis</p>

Table 1.2 shows the mental signs and symptoms associated with adenomyosis. Respondent M 1 was devastated when they heard the results from the doctor, and realized that when respondent M 1 was diagnosed, it could eventually turn into a cyst. Hearing the doctor's results shocked respondent M 1, who also recognized that even though they had been identified, the condition

might potentially develop into a cyst. When the respondent learned that the cyst was stable because it was not expanding, the respondent showed signs of relief.

The respondent stated:

“ Pero nung nagpa-consult ako sa ibang doctor, okay naman daw yung cysts, hindi *naman lumalaki, pero may adenomyosis daw ako.*”

But when I consulted another doctor, he said that the cysts were okay, they weren't growing, but he said I have adenomyosis.

“Hindi, ayos lang. Nung una, naiyak talaga ako nung sinabihan ako ng first doctor ko.”

No, it's okay. At the start, I cried when I was told by my first doctor.

“Oo nadarama ko ang depression ”

Yes I felt depressed

Mental signs and symptoms of the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis. The feeling of depression and anxiety is always experienced after patients have been diagnosed with adenomyosis. Barriers to self-management of patients with adenomyosis supports this statement (Rong Huang et. al., 2022).

Dealing with a chronic condition can be stressful and emotionally draining. Seeking support from mental health professionals, joining support groups, and practicing self-care can help women manage the emotional aspects of living with adenomyosis (Shree IVF Clinic. 2023). According to J. Lipman, et. al. (2019), Symptoms of depression caused by adenomyosis are common depression symptoms: loss of motivation, emotional ups and downs, decreased libido, irritability, anxiety, sleep/appetite disorders, fatigue, decreased energy, difficulty concentrating, and sometimes indigestion or headaches. A woman with adenomyosis may experience all of these symptoms or just a few.

Statement of the Problem 2. What are the perceived experiences of a mother diagnosed with Adenomyosis in terms of:

a. Physical

b. Emotional

c. Mental

Problem 2

Table 2 Physical, Emotional, and Mental Checklist of the Perceived Experiences of the Mother with Adenomyosis

Experiences	Physical	Mental	Emotional
Response	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abdominal pain <input type="checkbox"/> Headache <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pelvic pain <input type="checkbox"/> Constipation <input type="checkbox"/> Bloating <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Weight changes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fatigue <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heavy menstrual bleeding <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Increased menstrual cramps <input type="checkbox"/> Urinary urgency or frequency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anxiety <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Depression <input type="checkbox"/> Sleep deprivation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Difficulty concentrating <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Irritability <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lack of motivation towards daily activities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fatigue <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stress <input type="checkbox"/> Mood swings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Feelings of helplessness or hopelessness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Frustration with treatment options <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anger towards the condition and its impact on daily life <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Overwhelmed by managing symptoms while caring for family <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sense of isolation or loneliness due to difficulty discussing condition with others <input type="checkbox"/> Loss of self-esteem or confidence due to physical limitations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sadness over the impact on quality of life <input type="checkbox"/> Hopefulness for relief or improvement in symptoms through treatment or support. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anxiety about the progression of the condition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Difficulty in focusing or making decisions <input type="checkbox"/> Feelings of inadequacy or worthlessness due to limitations in activities

Table 2.1 shows the physical, emotional, and mental checklist of the perceived experiences of the mother with adenomyosis.

Statement of the Problem 3. What are common coping mechanisms used by a mother diagnosed with Adenomyosis when dealing with their medical condition in terms of:

a. Social Coping

b. Emotional Coping

c. Beliefs Coping

Problem 3

a. Did your family and friends help you cope with the medical condition you're dealing with? (yes or no)

If yes, how? If not, why?

b. Has your medical condition led to the formation of new relationships?

c. How did you maintain your relationships with others while experiencing this type of medical condition?

Table 3.1 Social Coping Mechanisms Used by the Mother with Adenomyosis

Respondents	Key Quote(s)	Code(s)	Theme(s)
M 1	<p>Yes, I have a friend whose spouse is a nurse, she said, "just trust, just pray," words of encouragement. Even her spouse, even my daughter, she said, "just trust, just trust," she said. So when I had my checkup again, with you, I was extremely grateful.</p> <p>Oh, not really, it's still the same, my old friends are still the same.</p> <p>It's just that, pretending I don't have any medical condition, like that, pretending I'm okay, my body is okay, but when for example they ask me, "oh, you have this kind of medical condition?," and I say but it's okay, it's just that, I just pray to God, that's where I hold on."</p>	<p>Family and friends helped cope with the medical condition</p> <p>Faithfulness</p> <p>Gratefulness</p> <p>Maintained relationships</p> <p>Pretending to be fine</p> <p>Acceptance</p>	<p>Social coping mechanisms used by the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis</p>

Table 3.1 shows the positive outcome of keeping relationships with loved ones while having adenomyosis. Socializing gives respondent M 1' love and support throughout her medical journey. Respondent M 1 also mentioned that pretending has become her coping mechanism to prevent thinking about her medical condition while interacting with others. It indicates a dislike for the mother to talk about her medical condition.

The respondent stated:

“Oo, may kaibigan ako na ang asawa ay nars, sinabi niya, “tiwala lang, magdasal ka lang,” mga salitang pampalakas-loob. Pati na rin ang asawa niya, pati ang anak ko, sinabi niya, “tiwala lang, tiwala lang”, sabi niya. Kaya nang magpunta ako ulit para sa aking checkup, kasama ka, lubos akong nagpapasalamat.”

Yes, I have a friend whose spouse is a nurse, she said, "just trust, just pray," words of encouragement. Even her spouse, even my daughter, she said, "just trust, just trust," she said. So when I had my checkup again, with you, I was extremely grateful.

“Kaya lang, kunwari wala akong medical condition, ganyan, kunwari okay lang, okay na katawan ko,”

It's just that, pretending I don't have any medical condition, like that, pretending I'm okay, my body is okay.

“Tinatanong nila ako, “oh, may ganitong kondisyon ka?” at sinasabi ko, pero okay lang, ganun lang, nananalangin lang ako sa Diyos, doon ako kumakapit.”

They ask me, "oh, you have this kind of medical condition?" and I say but it's okay, it's just that, I just pray to God, that's where I hold on.

As Aflakseir (2014) posits, social support serves as a protective barrier against stress and its negative effects, offering invaluable resources for coping and resilience. For the mother facing adenomyosis, the support of her family and friends provides a vital source of strength and comfort. Moreover, social coping mechanisms not only mitigate the immediate impact of adenomyosis on the individual but also foster long-term mental well-being. By fostering a sense of belonging and connectedness, social support nurtures psychological resilience, enabling individuals to adapt to the changes and uncertainties that accompany their condition (Ozbay et al., 2015). Therefore, in considering the holistic care of individuals diagnosed with adenomyosis, it becomes imperative to acknowledge and harness the power of social coping mechanisms (Huang et al., 2021).

a. How did you divert your attention from your medical condition?

b. Is your coping strategy helpful in overcoming your fear and sadness while experiencing this particular medical condition?

Table 3.2 Mental Coping Mechanisms Used by the Mother with Adenomyosis

Respondents	Key Quote(s)	Code(s)	Theme(s)
M 1	<p>Oh well, I just think about it when I feel the symptoms, but after that, nothing.</p> <p>Yes, I always keep myself busy, and then I always, I always focus on work, I'm focused on work now.</p>	<p>Not much of a problem</p> <p>Keeping herself busy</p>	Mental coping mechanisms used by the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis

Table 3.2 presents the mental coping mechanisms used by the respondent diagnosed with adenomyosis. Respondent M 1 discussed their strategies for coping with the challenges of adenomyosis. In assessing their mental coping strategies, Respondent M 1 discussed how they manage both the mental and emotional aspects of their illness. Throughout the discussion, respondent M 1 mentioned that they only think about their symptoms when they feel them, including their approach to dealing with symptoms and their focus on work as a distraction.

The respondent stated:

"Ay ano, bale na iisip ko lang naman sya pag nakaka ramdam ako ng mga symptoms, pero after ng ano, wala naman."

Oh well, I just think about it when I feel the symptoms, but after that, nothing.

"Ginagawa ko palagi busy yung sarili ko, tapos nag a-ano Ako palagi, nag f-focus ako sa trabaho, focus kasi ako sa trabaho ngayon eh."

Yes, I always keep myself busy, and then I always, I always focus on work, I'm focused on work now.

Coping mechanisms help to divert from stressors, improve mood, promote pleasant feelings, and serve as a type of self-care. Distraction involves using behaviors such as watching television, exercising, reading, or engaging in other pleasurable activities to distract oneself from the stressful event. Distraction is a passive coping strategy in that the person copes without directly confronting the situation or trying to solve the problem (Allen, A. B., & Leary, M. R. 2010). Moreover, it's essential for women with adenomyosis to prioritize their mental health. Dealing with a chronic condition can be stressful and emotionally draining. Seeking support from mental health professionals, joining support groups, and practicing self-care can help women manage the emotional aspects of living with adenomyosis (Shree IVF Clinic, 2023).

a. Does your relationship with God deepen while experiencing this medical condition?

b. When you discovered your medical condition, did you participate more in religious acts?

Table 3.3 Beliefs Coping Mechanisms Used by the Mother with Adenomyosis

Respondents	Key Quote(s)	Code(s)	Theme(s)
M 1	<p>Yes, but before, I wasn't a regular churchgoer. My daughter always said, "Mom, let's go to church with Dad," but when I got sick, I said I always pray, but I don't attend church, but now, starting from that time, we started attending church regularly, even without my daughter.</p> <p>Yes, we joined Medicine Counter, it's a group of married couples. We joined those from Manila. We attended a 1 to 3 day seminar for married couples, and that's where we started joining church activities.</p>	<p>Deeper connection towards beliefs</p> <p>Faithfulness</p> <p>Participated more in religious acts</p>	<p>Spiritual coping mechanisms used by the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis</p>

Table 3.3 shows the respondent's connection towards beliefs, faithfulness, and engaging in religious activities as the respondent's coping mechanism following the diagnosis with adenomyosis. Respondent M 1 showed signs of a stronger spiritual belief while experiencing Adenomyosis. Additionally, respondent M 1's medical condition seems to have increased her faithfulness and participation with religious acts.

The respondent stated:

“Lagi sinasabi ng anak ko, “Ma, simba tayo ni Papa,” pero nung nagkasakit ako, sinabi ko palagi akong nagdarasal, pero hindi ako sumasamba, pero ngayon, simula noon, nagsimula kaming mag-attend ng simbahan nang regular, kahit wala na yung anak ko.”

My daughter always said, "Mom, let's go to church with Dad," but when I got sick, I said I always pray, but I don't attend church, but now, starting from that time, we started attending church regularly, even without my daughter.

“Sumali kami sa isang seminar para sa mga mag-asawa na tumatagal ng 1 hanggang 3 araw, at doon nagsimula kaming sumali sa mga gawain ng simbahan.”

We attended a 1 to 3 day seminar for married couples, and that's where we started joining church activities.

The study by Bourdon et al. (2021) supports the notion of utilizing spirituality and engaging in religious activities as coping mechanisms for individuals facing adenomyosis, indicating a correlation between the diagnosis and increased religious engagement among participants. Results suggest that faith becomes stronger in response to the challenges posed by the condition, showing how belief systems can aid individuals in managing their health struggles.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the findings gathered in this investigation, conclusions and recommendations.

Summary of Findings

This study entitled “**A Narrative Study On The Lived Experiences Of A Mother Diagnosed With Adenomyosis**” was done in order to identify the difficulty faced by a mother diagnosed with adenomyosis in their everyday lives in Puerto Princesa City.

For the first question, the researchers were able to find that the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis indeed experienced signs and symptoms, particularly physically, such as excessive menstrual bleeding and pelvic pain. The researchers were also able to find that the mother diagnosed with adenomyosis has indeed been affected mentally, thus contributing to the factor that made the respondent depressed.

The researchers discovered the respondent diagnosed with adenomyosis faces a wide range of physical, mental, and emotional challenges. These include symptoms such as abdominal and pelvic pain, weight changes, fatigue, heavy menstrual bleeding, increased cramps, anxiety, depression, difficulty concentrating, lack of motivation, stress, feelings of helplessness, frustration with treatment, anger, overwhelm, isolation, sadness, and anxiety about the condition's progression. These challenges collectively impact the respondents' overall well-being, making it difficult to manage daily tasks and make decisions. This finding aligns with the extensive range of physical, mental, and emotional

struggles faced by the respondent diagnosed with adenomyosis, highlighting the significant impact of the condition on the respondent's life.

The respondent diagnosed with adenomyosis experienced different kinds of struggles, one of the coping mechanisms of the patient is her family, who she truly trusts and is grateful to, as well as God, whom she prays to. She started joining health and religious organizations. She continues, claiming that in order to avoid upsetting her husband and kid, she ignores her illness and pretends to be fine.

Salient Findings

1. The participant experienced heavy menstrual bleeding and pelvic pain before the diagnosis.
2. Mental health seems to be affected after diagnosis, leading to depressive tendencies.
3. A sense of isolation due to the difficulty of discussing the condition was observed.
4. Anger and frustration with the condition and overwhelming emotions with managing the medical condition.
5. Coping mechanisms of the patient seem to be related to the participant's family, religious acts, and health organization support groups.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were formulated based on the findings obtained:

The physical signs and symptoms that the mother experienced are shown in Table 1.1, which are: lower abdomen pain, suffering from severe pain, prolonged menstruation, and pain in the pelvic area, which affects her daily activities. Signs and symptoms mentally shown in Table 1.2: The mother cried; she was depressed initially but showed signs of relief when the mother was informed that it was not dangerous.

Perceived experiences of the mother shown in table 2, which were excessive menstrual bleeding, pelvic pain, weight changes, fatigue, increased menstrual cramps for the physical. Anxiety, depression, difficulty concentrating, lack of motivation, stress, feelings of helplessness for the mental. Frustration with treatment, anger, overwhelm, isolation, sadness, and anxiety about the condition's progression for the emotional.

Social coping mechanisms used by the respondent diagnosed with adenomyosis are shown in table 3.1 which were pretending and a dislike to talk about the medical condition. Mental coping mechanisms used by the respondent diagnosed with adenomyosis shown in the table 3.2 which was keeping themselves busy in order to forget about the signs of adenomyosis despite being diagnosed. The respondent's connection towards spirituality, faithfulness, and engaging in religious activities as the respondent's coping mechanism is shown in table 3.3 which were performing religious practices and acts, such as joining health and religious organizations where many common groups of married couples participate.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

For Patients with Adenomyosis, it is recommended that the patients with adenomyosis create a group or organization for adenomyosis patients wherein they can share information, medical advice, and support with one another.

For the City Health Centers, it is recommended for the city health centers to enhance medical consultations and diagnostic capabilities for adenomyosis. Offer specialized healthcare for recognizing and managing adenomyosis effectively. It is recommended to promote support networks and awareness campaigns to increase understanding and recognition of adenomyosis among the general public.

For the Department of Health (DOH), It is recommended for the Department of Health (DOH) to create standard protocols for adenomyosis diagnosis and treatment, using research resources for innovative diagnostic tools and treatment methods, collaborating with advocacy groups to increase patient awareness, and implementing nationwide screening programs to identify and diagnose adenomyosis early for effective treatment.

For the Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth), it is recommended for the Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth) to review and update coverage policies for adenomyosis, consider expanding coverage to include comprehensive care packages, and collaborate with

healthcare providers and policymakers to address coverage gaps and improve reimbursement rates.

For the Future Researchers, it is recommended for future researchers to further research and understand the mechanisms and risk factors linked to adenomyosis, explore new treatment methods, collaborate with multidisciplinary teams, and assess the long-term impact on patients' health. This would contribute to the global knowledge base on adenomyosis.

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APPENDICES

Appendix F. Interview Guide for the Gynecologist

**"A NARRATIVE OF THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF A
MOTHER DIAGNOSED WITH ADENOMYOSIS"**

- 1) What is Adenomyosis? ✓
- 2) What are the types of Adenomyosis? ✓
- 3) Is the term used in the study correct? 2 ✓
- 4) Is the disease common, or rare? ✓
- 5) What are the symptoms and signs of this disease? (before and after) ✓
- 6) What age does Adenomyosis usually occur? ✓
- 7) Is the health history of the patient connected to the illness? ✓
- 8) Is there a connection between the Ovarian Dermoid Cyst and Adenomyosis? ✓
- 9) Is there a difference between the Ovarian dermoid Cyst and Adenomyosis? ✓
- 10) What is the cause of change in the previous diagnoses of the patient? ✓
- 11) Is there a connection between Fertility and Adenomyosis? (Yes or No) ✓
- 12) If yes, how does Adenomyosis affect Fertility? ✓
If no, how did the women become infertile? ✓

Appendix G. Questionnaire for the Respondent

"A NARRATIVE OF THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF A MOTHER DIAGNOSED WITH ADENOMYOSIS"

SOP 1 *Ends Questionnaire*

AGE

How old are you when you experienced the symptoms of Adenomyosis?

How old are you when you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

HEALTH HISTORY

Have you had any disease before you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis? (yes or no)

If yes what type of disease

Are you taking medication before you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

If yes, please elaborate

SOP 2

PHYSICAL *what?*

Have you experienced severe abdominal pain during the menstruation period?

Have you experienced having prolonged menstruation?

Have you experienced heavy menstruation?

Have you experienced severe pelvic pain?

Does the physical pain disrupt your daily activities? (yes or no)

If yes, how?

If no, why?

SOP 3

MENTAL

What were your reaction when you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

Have you ever felt fear when you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

-self

-family

-community

Have you ever experienced depression after you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

Have you ever felt insecurities after you were diagnosed with Adenomyosis?

Have you ever felt out of place as a:

-mother

-woman

SOP 4

SOCIAL

Did your family and friends help you cope with the disease you're dealing with? (yes or no)

-if yes, how?

-if no, why?

Has your disease led to the formation of new relationships?

How did you maintain your relationships with others while experiencing this type of disease?

MENTAL

How did you divert your attention from your disease?

Is your coping strategy helpful in overcoming your fear and sadness while experiencing this particular disease?

RELIGIOUS *beliefs*

Does your relationship with god deepen while experiencing this disease?

When you discovered your disease, did you participate more in religious act?

MENTAL
 → What are ^{first} things that come into your mind when you experience the signs and symptoms of ADM?
 Have you felt fear when you experience the signs and symptoms of ADM?

Appendix H. Checklist for the Respondent

CHECKLIST

I. Experiences in terms of physical, emotional, and mental

Directions: The researchers is currently conducting a research entitled, "A NARRATIVE STUDY ON THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF A MOTHER DIAGNOSED WITH ADENOMYOSIS". Please answer the checklist honestly and without any mental reservations by ticking (✓) the appropriate boxes or by filling in the blanks. Your responses will be treated with utmost concern and confidentiality.

Physical:

- Abdominal pain
- Headache
- Pelvic pain
- Constipation
- Bloating
- Weight changes
- Fatigue
- Heavy menstrual bleeding
- Increased menstrual cramps
- Urinary urgency or frequency
- Others (specify) _____

Mental:

- Anxiety
- Depression
- Sleep deprivation
- Difficulty concentrating
- Irritability
- Lack of motivation towards daily activities
- Fatigue
- Stress
- Mood swings
- Feelings of helplessness or hopelessness
- Others (specify) _____

Emotional:

- Frustration with treatment options
- Anger towards the condition and its impact on daily life
- Overwhelmed by managing symptoms while caring for family
- Sense of isolation or loneliness due to difficulty discussing condition with others
- Loss of self-esteem or confidence due to physical limitations
- Sadness over the impact on quality of life
- Hopefulness for relief or improvement in symptoms through treatment or support.
- Anxiety about the progression of the condition
- Difficulty in focusing or making decisions
- Feelings of inadequacy or worthlessness due to limitations in activities
- Others (specify) _____

Signed consent forms, approval documents, and medical records are retained by the research adviser and are available upon reasonable request. These are withheld from publication to protect participant confidentiality.